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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	Sensitivity of High Voltage Enhancement GaN/AIGaN COTS power transistors to Radiation. (SHIVER)
Project TA identifier	TA11-368
General application	Space, High Reliability Ground Level, High energy accelerators
Type of test	SEE
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Date(s) of the experiment	27 to 31 / 01 / 2025
Facility	UCL HIF
Amount of access granted	16 h

Objectives of the experiments

The project shall implement heavy ion tests of several high voltage COTS GaN (typically above 600 V) References which have been selected based on their performance and testability against heavy ion irradiation facility. The investigation shall notably rely on a systematic test of large batch size in order to characterize potential sensitivity variability and failure distribution law against destructive effects.

Experiment test report

Several investigations have highlighted an atypical behavior of GaN HEMTS under heavy ion irradiations. In particular, the JPL Team did observe a large discrepancy between different date codes of first and second generation from EPC GaN/AIGaN Transistors (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

The observed SOA is thus potentially difficult to predict without testing all lots and increasing their sample size in order to capture any potential variability which could stems from process variability. It shall be stressed that other EEE and standard RHA are surveyed for Single Event Effects on a process/wafer fabrication site basis and only Dose effects are surveyed at a Wafer lot level. Understanding this apparent discrepancy in behavior is thus of importance as additional test and lead time could be required in the wake of selection of Power GaN technology for space electronics design.

The study has explored the evolution of sensitivity within two different batches of COTS GaN/AlGaN HEMTs. This study has been designed in order to understand the source of variability regarding Single Event Testing that could stem from sample preparation, notably regarding GaN/AlGaN packaged parts.

The study is organized according to the next figure.

- Sample Opening
- Assembly
- Testing
- Heavy Ion test
- Post Campaign Characterization

The selected test vehicle is the GS065030 from GaN Systems. This device is a 650 V 50 mOhm 30 A GaN FET HEMTs on Silicon packaged in a DFN 8 mm x 8 mm package. The die dimensions are measured as 1.8 mm x 4.2 mm. Two batches have been characterized coming from different procurement with date codes distant of 21 weeks. Despite differences in the packaging formulation, noticeable during deprocessing, no visual differences have been identified at die level between the two date codes.

A total of 39 samples were prepared thanks to Microwave Induced Plasma de-capsulating (MIP) and tested in different test conditions. The next figures illustrate the quality of the sample preparation which keeps integrity of bonding, pads and die surface cleanliness. Those parts are tested prior and after de-capsulating in order to check their electrical performance before Single Event Test Campaign.

The next table provides the ion beam selected from UCL HIF Facility in order to explore destructive SOA domain.

Ion	Energy [MeV]	Range [µm Si]	LET in Si [MeV.cm ² .mg ⁻¹]
¹²⁴ Xe ³⁵⁺	995	73.1	62.5
¹⁰³ Rh ³¹⁺	972	88,7	45,8
⁸⁴ Kr ²⁵⁺	769	94,2	32,4

In detail, a total of 39 samples were tested with iso-fluence step runs from a start bias of about 200 V to failure onset with a VDS stepping of 20 V and Gate bias fixed to V_{GS} = 0 V. This test mode has been applied for every irradiation run. The summary of the run conditions is as follows:

- N1VY Datecode: 27 samples tested.
- 2H55 Datecode: 12 samples tested.
- 8 Runs performed under Krypton 10⁵ ions/cm² step fluence on 4 N1VY and 4 2H55 samples
- 3 Runs performed under Rhodium 10⁵ ions/cm² step fluence on 2 N1VY and 1 2H55 samples
- 31 Runs performed under Xenon Normal Incidence on 21 N1VY and 10 2H55 samples
 - Of which runs 9 runs with 10⁶ ions/cm²step fluence (8 on N1VY, 1 2H55)

A good homogeneity of failure domain and cross-section is observed. The effect of larger fluence steps contributes to lowering the SOA figure by a factor of 10 to 15 %.

- Thanks to the available beam time and homogeneity measured between the first sequence of runs, an exploration has been performed in the following conditions:
 - Additional Xenon Runs at High Temperature and Normal Incidence: 2 Run on 1 Sample N1VY and 1 Sample 2H55
 - Additional Xe Runs Tilt and Tilt and Roll 90° at Room Temperature: 6 Run on 3 Samples N1VY

The summary of SOA figures is provided in the next chart.

In conclusion, despite the extensive beam conditions, the study did not allow us to identify a clear difference in behavior between the two tested batches of GS065030 COTS GaN FET from GaN Systems. So as an outcome of the present study, nothing would prevent to address this device technology with the actual SEE approach recommended in the ECSS RHA standard. As a benefit, this study has allowed to gain confidence in the fact that such a technology hasn't necessarily an unwanted variability of its SEE performance from lot to lot. Further efforts would be to:

- In the future and given the process nature, the end-user should continue to survey the risk of variability on this technology. One shall then extend this effort to other types of devices (Medium voltage) or GaN ICs in order to determine their suitability and potentially vertical GaN technology.
- Optimize the use of step-wise Safe Operating Area which allows to improve the definition of the SOA region above the sensitivity onset and could be beneficial on part with higher softness or likely to ion leakage current degradation.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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